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JEM - Joining Educational Mathematics

Final Report

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eContentplus

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a multiannual Community programme to make digital content in Europe more accessible, usable and exploitable.

¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

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2 Project Objectives

The Joining Educational Mathematics thematic network stated as goals the tasks of bringing together expertise required to enrich eContent for mathematics, of maintaining agreed relevant standards and of delivering synoptic high-quality user support information on technologies for e-learning mathematics.

The real challenge of e-learning is to provide eContent that improves the ways in which students learn and instructors teach. The design and the production of high-quality digital content in mathematics has turned out to be harder than expected, the main reason being that it requires a blend of competences including those of professional mathematicians, software engineers, publishers, and mathematics educators. JEM addresses this challenge by creating a venue where educators, mathematicians, and software developers may exchange experiences and collaborate to the creation of better eContent.

3 Consortium

The JEM Consortium comprises 20 nodes representing leading developers of semantic web technologies for the representation of mathematics, mathematics content stakeholders and experienced distributors of software and eLearning solutions all across Europe.

JEM partners offer advanced learning software solutions and a wide range of ICT tools to enhance mathematics teaching. The network coordinator, University of Helsinki, has a long standing cooperation with Technical University of Eindhoven, Jacobs University and NAG Ltd, in research on representation and software for the electronic communication of mathematics. The commercial partner Maths for More has been developing and marketing a suite of advanced calculation and presentation tools for mathematics education with emphasis on Internet technology solutions, most notably WIRIS CAS, a multilingual on-line platform for mathematics calculation and contents. WIRIS is actively used by thousands of students and teachers in Spain, Italy, Belgium, The Netherlands, Luxemburg and Estonia. WIRIS tools are multilingual, serving students in English, French, Spanish, Italian, Dutch/Flemish, Estonian, Catalan and Basque language.

University of Birmingham hosts the main scientist in charge of STACK, an open-source software system for mathematics assessment, with Maxima as computer algebra back engine, able to generate exercises from an algorithmic template and to automatically grade the mathematical content within students' answers. STACK can be conveniently used to enhance the Moodle quizzes thus improving the popular learning environment. Technical University of Eindhoven is also offering an open-source solution for mathematics assessment as part of MathDox, an ensemble of software tools for creating Interactive Mathematical Documents. MathDox includes:

- an XML based language (based on DocBook) that offers markup support for the source texts of Interactive Mathematical Documents;
- a document server , rendering interactive mathematical documents from source text and interactively obtained information;
- mathematical services, providing connections with Computer Algebra Systems like Mathematica, Maxima and GAP via OpenMath phrasebooks.

Another format well suited for interactive documents in mathematics is OMDOC, actively developed by Jacobs University that focuses research on semantic web technologies for mathematics, with technologies that demonstrate the versatility of a rich representation.

German partners, RWTH Aachen University and ISN Oldenburg, both develop and employ ad-hoc learning environments for teaching applications of mathematics in Statistics and Physics.

Authors and users of online educational material for mathematics and institutions offering online courses and distance education are important members in the JEM community: they give feedback to developers on what is effective. Universiteit van Amsterdam has a wide experience in using ICT-supported courseware: their Coach system has been successfully used in high schools across the Netherlands for several years. Three JEM partners represent distance universities: the German FernUniversität Hagen, the Spanish UNED National Distance University of Education, and the Catalonian Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. All of them deliver instruction purely online and have created a wide collection of learning resources. Universidade de Lisboa, Buskerud University College, and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki are traditional higher education institution where the introduction of ICT support is taking place gradually. Together with AMSTEL Institute of UvA, the Norwegian University of Science and Technology bridges the gap towards mathematics teacher education by training teachers to be in best practices for ICT in mathematics.

Each partner has specific dissemination channels, whether students, or organizations or professional societies, however the JEM network also includes the commercial publisher Liguori Editore and the major international academic society of professional mathematicians, the European Mathematical Society.

4 Project Results/Achievements

In order to improve the quality of eContent in Mathematics, JEM pursued activities aimed at identifying and reaching out to eContent stakeholders, at coordinating the development of mathematical markup languages and at promoting the use of mathematics markup for mathematics in e-learning.

JEM reached out to involve researchers from science accessibility, teacher education, mathematics education, and instructional design and educational psychology in the events it organized. The focus of each JEM event has aimed at creating awareness towards important aspects or eContent by invited leading experts in these areas and by organizing events at conferences in neighbouring fields.

JEM was present with a workshop and an exhibition booth at ICME11, the International Congress on Mathematical Education, in its eleventh edition held in Monterrey, Mexico, July 6 - 13, 2008. The last meeting of JEM was a satellite workshop at ICWL 2009, the 8th International Conference on Web-based Learning, last 19-21 August 2009, at RWTH in Aachen, Germany. Before, the 4th JEM meeting had taken place alongside the 4th European Workshop on Mathematical & Scientific e-Contents, at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, on September 11-13, 2008 while the 2nd JEM meeting had been joint with the 8th OpenMath meeting during a weeklong sequence of international scientific at the Research Institute for Symbolic Computation (RISC) in Austria in the summer of 2007. Specific focus was targeted in JEM seminars, in particular the ones organized by Jacobs University on identifying and supporting (scientific) communities in education and research or those by University of Helsinki on new and emerging technologies, such as vodcasting, for

mathematics. JEM members have organized training activities both at national and international level, for instance introducing technologies for automated assessment in mathematics at the Joint European Summer School on Technology Enhanced Learning 2009, in Terchova, Slovakia and at the Finnish ITK, Interactive Technology in Education, conference in Hämeenlinna in April 2009.

The JEM network has pursued its goal not only by organizing events but foremost by setting up a web 2.0 portal at <http://jem-thematic.net> that distributes and disseminates the work of the JEM partners and community members. All presentations and publications associated with the network's events can be downloaded from the publication section on the web pages. The portal also includes a repository of learning resources. Besides publications, activities of the JEM community are made visible through the web pages as news announcements, blog entries, software descriptions and case studies. Each member of the online JEM community is able to create content that is automatically published on the portal. Moderators can edit content further whereas any members can add translations.

Areas for collaborative editing of wiki pages are predisposed for the major user groups in the community: developers, authors and users of eContent. Depending on the specific interest of the member, it is possible to post descriptions of software and services (targeting developers), of case studies (targeting users) or share a learning resource (targeting authors). Each post can be commented and rated or reviewed. Members, who wish to stay up-to-date with reactions to their posts or new postings on the JEM portal, may opt to do so by using the subscription buttons and by RSS feeds.

Currently the community lists 286 registered members, approved by the administrators, who have contributed 284 publications, 27 Software and services descriptions, 12 Case studies and 76 Learning resources.

JEM - Joining Educational Mathematics
eContentPlus Thematic Network

285 Members | 284 Publications | 27 Software and Services | 12 Case studies | 76 Learning resources

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NETWORK MEETINGS
View Edit Outline Track Translation Access control

The JEM Network will organize a series of workshops on a bi-annual basis and a number of events at other conferences. Here is a summary of what is happening.

Meeting	Date	Location
1st JEM Workshop+Calculus	8-9-10 February, 2007	Lisbon, PT
2nd JEM Workshop: Joint with OpenMath	25-26 July, 2007	Linz, A
3rd JEM Workshop	26-28 February, 2008	Barcelona, ES
4th JEM Workshop	11 September, 2008	Trondheim, NO
5th JEM Workshop	26-27 November 2008	Paris, FR
6th JEM Workshop	21 August 2009	Aachen, D
JEM Seminar: Scientific Communities of Practice 2007	30 August, 2007	Bremen, D
JEM Seminar: New and Emerging Technologies in Mathematics Education	17-18 August, 2007	Helsinki, FI
Mathematical e-content: expressing, manipulating and retrieving mathematics	24 April, 2008	Copenhagen, DK
JEM Seminar: VodMath, Vodcasting Mathematics	23-24 May, 2008	Helsinki, FI
JEM Seminar: Scientific Communities of Practice 2008	27 June, 2008	Bremen, D
JEM Workshop at ICHE11: eLearning Mathematics	9 July, 2008	Montreux, CH
Symposium on "Math tutoring: tools and feedback"	18-19 September, 2008	Heerlen, NL
JEM School: GF for Grammars Developers	20-29 April, 2009	Online course
JEM School: STACK, a System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer	1 June 2008	Torshavn, FO

RECENT BLOG POSTS

- PDF viewer test
- Observations from ICWL 2009
- Interview on the Learning Repository with the University of North Texas
- Interview on the Learning Repository with the University of North Texas
- Real Time Assessment
- Podcasting vs. Lecturing
- Improved navigation on the JEM site
- Educational uses of wikis
- MathML displayed natively in Safari, on iPhone
- Mac Pro vs MacBook Air in Movie Production

UPCOMING EVENTS

- Knowledge and Experience Management (FGWM 2009) (14 days) (Event)
- The Workshop on E-Inclusion in Mathematics and Science 2009 (WEIMS'09) - Call for papers (Event)

Register and login to add your learning resource.

ONLINE SINGLE VARIABLE CALCULUS
Submitted by Mka.Sappala on Thu, 2008/03/06 - 13:21

The Online Single Variable Calculus is a full course at university level covering topics from Real Numbers, Functions, Differentiation, Integration, Series and Differential Equations. Each topic is organized in a module consisting of a Ten Minute Talk accompanied by Open Problems and Solved Problems. The material has been designed especially for online delivery.

Add new comment 3850 reads

VIDEO LESSONS IN LINEAR ALGEBRA
Submitted by andean on Tue, 2008/01/15 - 13:25

Collection of Video Lessons in Linear Algebra. (The lessons are in Norwegian.)

Add new comment 3227 reads

HOW ROUND IS YOUR CIRCLE?
Submitted by sargenic on Thu, 2008/03/06 - 13:12

How do you draw a straight line? How do you determine if a circle is really round? These may sound like simple or even trivial mathematical problems, but to an engineer the answers can mean the difference between success and failure. This website contains interactive materials to support the book How Round Is Your Circle?, by John Bryant and Chris Sangwin. This book invites readers to explore many of the same fundamental questions that working engineers deal with every day. It also illustrates how physical models are created from abstract mathematical ones.

Add new comment 3761 reads

The JEM repository deserves special attention as it has been developed as a set of modules for a popular content management system called Drupal. The modules are freely available. The accompanying detailed guide on how the portal has been implemented, "How to build a learning repository on Drupal (5.x) and PHP 5.1.x +", is one of the most popular pages of the portal. The JEM repository is now also running at the

Accessible Science portal, <http://www.ascience-thematic.net> and at INITE, Universidad Tecnológica de México, who also contributed the Spanish translation of the guide. Several JEM partners are involved with developing or using national or thematic portals, e.g. <http://www.wizmo.nl>, <http://oer.uoc.edu> and <http://www.physik-multimedial.de/lili>, these will have to be integrated to the JEM portal harvest search. The JEM repository has been

developed in conformance with the LOM² (import/export) and OAI-PMH³ standard for open archives. This has recently allowed the repository to be integrated into the ARIADNE search from the foundation for the European Knowledge Pool thus giving contributing authors greater visibility.

The use of metadata for resource description is just one aspect of best practice for eContent. The JEM network has been promoting the use of semantic markup in mathematical content by contributing to the standardization efforts of alignment of two leading representation languages, MathML and OpenMath. The past 3 years have seen the progressive evolution that will lead to a unified markup language with the forthcoming release of the new version of MathML and of OpenMath, Version 3. A new set of Content Dictionaries for MathML has been recently accepted by the OpenMath Society and will form the backbone for the new Content-MathML representation. This achievement will strengthen both OpenMath and MathML as standard and impact projects such as Inter2Geo, Interoperable Interactive Geometry for Europe, and SCience, Symbolic Computation Infrastructure for Europe, that have chosen OpenMath to ground the communication protocols for the next generation of dynamic geometry and computational systems.

5 Target Users & their Needs

The JEM community blends the expertise of developers of supporting technologies for mathematics, of authors and users of eContent for teaching mathematics. All these user groups are able, through the infrastructure setup by the JEM network, to exchange views on how technology should be developed and used in an educational context, thus covering several aspects involved in employing eContent in mathematical education.

Developers of technologies that may enhance doing and teaching mathematics on computers are supported by JEM in their dissemination efforts by the pages listed under “Software and services”. These pages are designed to give synoptic, informative descriptions, links and software demonstrations to those who wish to further develop or use the software in authoring eContent. After registration on the JEM site, it is possible to create such a description page and to maintain it regularly, using it as a way to direct JEM readers to one's own products. Since each registered JEM member may host a personal blog on the JEM portal, a developer's blog can also provide a way to publish news concerning releases, new features, patches, and be a way to activate the interest of the user community. Newsflashes and events are yet another mechanism for members to disseminate activities of interest that are also distributed via the JEM RSS feed⁴.

The dissemination infrastructure designed for authors of eContent and in particular, for authors wishing to share or recommend learning resources, is the fully LOM-compliant repository hosted by JEM. It has been integrated with the free-tagging mechanism whereby a resource can be described by keywords chosen by the author as well as with a classification using standard metadata for mathematical resources. Because the JEM repository is a registered OAI-PMH data server that can be queried by federated search engines and harvesters adhering to the open archive initiative, it increases the visibility of any eContent published via JEM and broadens the access to digital mathematical resources for eLearning and eScience. To facilitate the registration of resources previously registered elsewhere and to promote consistency among repositories, authors may import LOM metadata directly and export it should they need to include LOM metadata in the preparation of learning modules. To promote users' interaction, any resource can be commented and reviewed; hopefully

² <http://www.imsproject.org/metadata>

³ <http://www.openarchives.org>

⁴ <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/rss.xml>

following the guidelines described in the documents “[Evaluation Criteria for eContent Quality](#)” and “[Establishment of review process and related criteria for assessment](#)”, both available as JEM deliverables.

Users of eContent can be either instructors or students. Students can find resources for own study in the JEM repository whereas instructors can give valuable feedback to both developers and authors by interacting via the comments as mentioned above. More importantly, the JEM portal also aims to collect case studies that describe actual use of ICT in mathematics education, lessons learned, difficulties encountered and methodologies. This collection, reachable at <http://www.jem-thematic.net/view/casestudy>, is also intended for the mathematics educators and for researchers in mathematics education since each case study can provide pedagogical guidelines on where and how to introduce technology in eLearning mathematics, and can point to relevant literature.

In general, the JEM network has build a community whose interest is exemplified by the JEM “tag cloud”, here below:

3.1.6 Matrices 3.2 Linear Algebra 3.2.1 Systems of Linear Equations 3.2.5 Linear Transformations 6. Calculus
 active Active Assessment atomic Atomic authoring Calculus Calculus Call for paper Call for
 participation Collection Community Content with atomic or collection
 structure deliverable Easy English (en) Event planning Final final Firefox Gauss algorithm
 General Issues German (de) high high Higher Education higher
 education JEM JEM Event JEM News JEM Partner JEM portal JEM Portal JEM workshop
 Learner linear transformations LOM repository MathML matrices Medium Meeting News Norwegian
 (no) OpenMath podcasts Portal SCOOP Semantic markup Simulation simulation Support
 Technologies University First Cycle XML technology xs-stokes

Each tag is a specialized dissemination channel associated to a RSS newsfeed published by the portal. Take for instance the tag "OpenMath", all news, blogs, events and pages, which are tagged with it, are listed on <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/taxonomy/term/8> and any reader interested in OpenMath may subscribe to it by pointing its reader to the corresponding feed <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/taxonomy/term/8/feed>, or by clicking on the RSS icon in the browser. This mechanism can be readily employed by all JEM community member to promote their activities, and to keep up-to-date with their interest.

6 Underlying Content

Content produced by members of the JEM network is contributed to the portal on a volunteer basis with the aim to showcase eContent for mathematics that uses a blend of technologies.

At the time of writing, the publications available from the web site increased from 183 of last year to 284 items including papers, slide presentations and tutorials. In general, all presentations delivered during a JEM sponsored event are archived on the website as well as the network deliverables⁵. Sample resources at the portal have grown from 27 to 76 resources all fully registered using LOM metadata, in addition to 12 case studies and 27 descriptions of software and services.

Examples of resources include full online courses comprising a collection of material, but also pointers to videos and applets and content that can be used as ancillary material. For instance, TU/e and UvA have worked on synchronization of assessments and standardization of tests

⁵ <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/publications/deliverables>

that are uploaded to the WIZMO portal as part of the Dutch project NKBW⁶, their activity is widely documented in their progress reports available on JEM. In addition, TU/e has setup a website, Wortel TU/e⁷ to improve the transition of students from high school by offering mathematical material suitable for self-study and has registered this resource in the JEM repository. The site contains study material for high school mathematics calculus and linear algebra and interactive exercises and digital examination possibilities. More than 1000 students who carried out over 50.000 exercises have used the site. UPC has registered a full course, complete with 142 exercises, to introduce Stokes and Gauss theorems to mathematicians, physicists and engineers⁸.

Several JEM members also author courses for distance education. FernUniversität Hagen registered their flashcard-based content used in single variable calculus distance course. Likewise, University of Helsinki has reorganized its extensive collection of interactive exercises and produced a full online course on Calculus, which won the Rector's prize for technology in education.

Resources and content published via the JEM portal is subject to community review and as such it is the JEM community that decides its quality. Ultimately, users are able to evaluate quality also based on community usage, for instance by comparing the number of downloads or of hits of a certain resource. This number is displayed publicly under each post and yields a rough measure of usage. For the Software and Services description, the most read entry is that of the MathDox Formula editor, with 6213 hits, followed closely by the SWiM Semantic Wiki software. According to the logs⁹, the most popular blog entry is the one entitled “TPAC 2007 Audio Streamcast” by Olga.Caprotti, with 13650 reads, while the most popular publication is by J.H. Davenport, “OpenMath: Symbols, CDs and Signatures”, from the 2nd JEM Workshop, with 9424 reads.

7 Summary of Activities

Members of the JEM network have been and continue to work in improving the creation and utilization of eContent in mathematics education. With new developments in web technologies, training courses for math educators, production of sample content, they contribute knowhow to every stakeholder in the process. The JEM web portal, in adopting LOM, OAI-PMH, MathML, tries to set an example of best practice and to promote a wider spread of these standards. As example, the JEM repository is ready to become interoperable with the repositories run by members such as ISN Oldenburg, UvA and UOC. These partners will make their learning resources available by exporting the metadata.

Support for representation and communication standards for mathematics has continued with relevant work by D. Carlisle of NAG and M. Kohlhase of JACU on the OpenMath Content Dictionaries for MathML 3 which have been voted and accepted during the OpenMath Workshop in July 2009 to be officially released and hosted by openmath.org. The MathML 3 candidate recommendation is planned for release during Autumn 2009 and is currently being reviewed by the working group. The adoption of the mechanism of Content Dictionaries by both languages will have a positive impact since software implementers will need to provide interfaces to one encoding only. In addition to this, the release of the STIX fonts in the public domain will make it easier to widely distribute mathematical documents without relying on proprietary fonts, which are typically only available in non-standard encodings and formats.

⁶ <http://www.nkbw.nl>

⁷ (<http://wortel.tue.nl>)

⁸ <http://jem-thematic.net/en/node/1385>

⁹ <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/popular/alltime>

JEM has disseminated the recent progress in the support of OpenMath, mainly as a result of the Intergeo and SCIENCE efforts. More precisely, TU/e contributed to the Java library for SCSCP and OpenMath released in February 2009 at <http://java.symcomp.org> within the Symbolic Computation Infrastructure for Europe project (SCIENCE). All systems participating in the project (GAP, KANT, Maple, MuPAD) offer both client and server support for the SCSCP protocol while support across systems is currently being pursued.

OpenMath is also adopted by the Intergeo project to be the underlying format used in a web-based platform (opened at <http://i2geo.net/>) for mathematics teachers to find, edit and even add dynamic geometry resources. TU/e and M4M are JEM partners involved in the Intergeo efforts. The Intergeo file format is a file format designed to describe any construction created with a Dynamic Geometry System (DGS). As a first application, the format can be used to interchange content between geometric software. The Intergeo common file format was released in July 2009 with a new collection of symbols in the so called “symbol list layer”. OpenMath is used to declare an exhaustive enumeration of valid geometric elements, constraints and styles that can be used to generate a construction. Although the symbols have been chosen to be part of a DGS construction, actually, they could live independently and be used for other purposes. In the current release, the format is restricted to the geometry in the plane, although a future extension to the space can be envisioned.

Jacobs University (JACU) and TU/e have continued to develop software and tools handling the OpenMath extension languages OMDoc and MathDox. The editorial work on Content Dictionaries, mentioned above, namely the creation and discussion of collections of symbols definitions and declarations for OpenMath, has benefitted from the SWiM¹⁰, Semantic Wiki, platform developed at JACU. Here above is a screenshot of a discussion hosted on the SWiM.

Exercise.

Simplify as far as possible: $\frac{6}{6} + \frac{6}{4}$.

$\frac{6}{6} + \frac{6}{4} =$

$+$ $-$ \cdot \wedge \vee $\cos()$ $\sqrt{\quad}$ $\int dx$ $\int dx$
 $<$ \leq $=$ \geq $>$ $\sin()$ $\sqrt{\quad}$ $\prod_{n=}$ $\sum_{n=}$ $\det()$
 π e i ∞ $\tan()$ $\{\}$ $()$ $()$ $(:)$
 $\frac{\quad}{\quad}$ $||$ $!$ e $\ln()$ $\log(10,)$ $()$ $()$ $(:)$

The MathDox FormulaEditor has been developed for students to enter formulas in an e-learning environment. It has a two-dimensional WYSIWYG interface but can produce a semantic representation of the formula. Since no plugins need to be installed in the browser to use the editor, it can be easily integrated into existing HTML pages. Extensibility is possible as TU/e distributes the javascript code under an open source license.

¹⁰ <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/node/316>

Jacobs University has continued to develop the javascript API for OMDoc-based Active Documents (JOBAD) and the semantic wiki SWiM and presented a vision for their integration into an eLearning environment during the final JEM meeting. Developers of OMDoc-based applications may now use the JOMDoc API to handle the XML formatted documents and in future will also be able to store native OMDoc documents in the TNTBase XML repository, which is designed ad-hoc for mathematical queries.

JEM has been trying to strengthen the cooperation with the mathematics education community over the past 2 years, starting with the collocation of workshops and meetings at events such as the International Conference of Mathematics Education. During the past year, A. Heck of UvA has been keynote presenter at the conference on Computer Algebra and Dynamic Geometry Systems in Mathematics Education (CADGME) and at The Ninth International Conference on Technology in Mathematics Teaching. Moreover, also at CADGME 2009, R. Eixarch from Maths For More presented the workshop “WIRIS, tools for web based learning environments (Moodle, Drupal, Joomla, Blogs)”. JEM has also organized teachers training activities, in particular TU/e has prepared online and paper material and organized meetings for high-school teachers, and teacher training courses for the new subject area ‘Wiskunde D’ (‘Mathematics D’) that started in 2007-2008 in the Netherlands. UH has organized a JEM school on using web based exercises in mathematics learning as an afternoon workshop in the ITK conference, the largest eLearning event aimed at Finnish practitioners in polytechnics, universities and high schools.

A. Sanne from NTNU is coordinating the activities of the GeoGebra Institute of Norway¹¹ (NGI). NGI has trained more than 50 teachers and teacher educators as GeoGebra instructors. The training started last December 2008 as an online activity using Moodle, and ended up with a workshop at NTNU in Trondheim in February 2009. NGI in partnership with LAMIS (Landslaget for matematikk i skolen), the Norwegian association for mathematics teachers, will give 20 workshops all around Norway during 2009. About 10 workshops were organized in the Spring term, and the next 10 will take place this autumn.

Future activities have been also planned by Open University of Catalonia (UOC) and (Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia) UNED who co-organized the workshop “Matemática a Distância no Contexto Ibérico” in Lisbon. Concrete results of this event are the decision to organize an annual conference inviting universities of the Iberoamerican area, with the next one to take place at UNED in April 2010, but also a trans-national agreement in order to facilitate the interchange of students and teachers, the intent to design of a joint PhD program between UNED-Aberta and new on-line courses for teachers, and the pursuit of new research projects on e-learning in a partnership between UOC, UNED and Aberta.

University of Birmingham has released a math editor called DragMath which can be used in Moodle but more importantly, a new version of the assessment system STACK, improved in its performance as a result of discussions with JEM partners. Also Maths for More has produced plugins for Moodle, including a chat application which allows to type mathematical expressions. UNED and UOC have integrated the WIRIS suite of tools from Maths for More in their learning environments. The figure below shows a discussion forum in aLF, UNED’s own learning environment, augmented by the WIRIS plugin for rendering mathematics.

¹¹ <http://www.geogebra.no>

Alternative learning environments are being studied also at Jacobs University with a specific attention to supporting scientific communities of practice and semantic wikis. Enhancements of wiki-like platforms for education are also done in Chalmers with software for automated multilingual translation of wiki pages. RWTH Aachen and ISN Oldenburg have continued to develop their subject-specific learning environments, EMILeA-stat for statistics and physik-multimedial for physics respectively.

8 Impact & Sustainability

The number of new national and international initiatives, which have been granted during the project's lifetime and involve some of the JEM members, gauges the impact of the JEM network on the future development of eContent in mathematics. We list a few collaborations however the full picture can only be grasped by reading through the partners progress reports¹² and in the section of related projects¹³ on the portal.

8.1 National funding

e-math++ at UOC, Open (accessible contents for free), quality (contents revised by university teachers) and collaborative (inter- university) web repository of mathematic-statistical contents generated in e-M@ath++ and EA2008-0151 projects from IN3's NET2LEARN group. This repository contains a variety of materials: explanatory texts, solved exercises, application examples, multimedia documents, etc. Its contents are classified following a specified taxonomy and can be accessed by using keywords through the portal's 'Subject' directory or by using it's own search engine.

ENGINE Creator-User-Referees-Interaction for professional retrieval of distributed multimedia objects in Physics at ISN. The goal of ENGINE is to connect different kinds of people who are concerned with elearning material like teachers, lecturers, students and authors, in particular a service for authors of physics' learning materials to exchange their experiences and knowledge.

i-MATH, Ingenio MATHEMATICA is a CONSOLIDER singular research project for the period 2006-2011 at UOC and UNED. It proposes a complete activity research program for Spanish mathematics, with the purpose of promoting and carrying out strategic actions of

¹² <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/about/progress>

¹³ <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/related>

national scope that qualitatively and quantitatively increase mathematical presence on the international scene, and in the Spanish system of science, technology and business and on the international scene.

Intelligent Feedback, e-learning tools for linear algebra that give feedback on the level of strategies. The Surf Intelligent Feedback project was a cooperation between Eindhoven University of Technology, Delft University of Technology, and the Open University.

Mathadore, web based, and highly interactive course material for high school mathematics in the Netherlands. Mathadore is still under development, but parts can be found at <http://www.mathadore.nl>. Mathadore makes use of the MathDox software as developed by the TU/e. Mathadore is a project of a consortium consisting of the foundation Math4All, Pragma ADE, an small company specialized in publishing on demand, and the Discrete Algebra and Geometry group of the TU Eindhoven.

MathAssess, at UB is a JISC project running in 2008-2009 that will utilize a version of the QTI toolkit (ASDEL, AQuRate, Minibix, R2Q2), extended to include the MathQTI specification in item authoring and rendering to handle mathematical elements. The goal is to enable the use of algebraic expressions within questions by incorporating a Computer Algebra System for rendering and for processing calculations. Tools for integration with the gradebooks at least on the Moodle are investigated.

MEL, Mathematical e-learning at the Spanish Universities, at UOC is a grant by the Department of Universities and Research of the Spanish Ministry of Education and Science to study of the educational technologies and ICT used in teaching and learning mathematics at the Spanish Universities.

NKBW 2, Nationale Kennisbank Basisvaardigheden Wiskunde (National Knowledge Bank on Basic Skills in Mathematics) funded by the SURF Foundation, a joint project with 18 Dutch higher education institutes, includes UvA and TU/e. It is a follow up of the NKBW. Aims are to provide (1) extension of the use of materials and experiences of 18 trajectories for transfer between secondary school and higher education via the NKBW repository, (2) improvement of the repository (3) convergence between secondary and tertiary education with regards to assessment of algebraic skills, and (4) use of diagnostic tests in 20 secondary schools and 18 trajectories for transfer between secondary school and higher education institutes.

PERSONAL(ONTO), Personalizing the Learning Process in Virtual Environments by means of Adaptive Formative Itineraries based on Reusable Learning. The Spanish Ministry of Education and Science project TIN2006-15107-C02-01/02 at UOC in partnership with UAH, Universidad de Alcalá, aims to provide a personalized learning process by means of adaptive formative itineraries, involving the use of learning object repositories and ontologies.

SELL, Automatic assessment and e-learning Logica, Innovative internal UOC Project. Development of an automatic tool used in the assessment and evaluation support in an e-learning course of Logic. Constructing a reusable, multilingual and usable tool for the e-learning assessment in a Logic e-learning course and carrying out a test to evaluate its effectiveness.

SIGMA, Special Interest Group Mathematics Activities, is an initiative of the SURF foundation (<http://www.surf.nl>), and aims at facilitating continuous learning paths in education in mathematics between secondary education and higher education. In this way it

intends to attack the problems regarding the transition 'from pupil to student' for mathematics. SIGMA is the platform for the exchange of knowledge, experiences and helps in addressing the problems of prerequisite mathematics. SIGMA concentrates on four main topics: content and education, assessment and testing, exchange and standardization, and the SIGMA award for best teacher and practice in education. SIGMA is a community rather than a single project. The community accommodates many projects, programs and working groups. Current projects are MathMatch, NKBW and Webspijkeren. Current workgroups are engaged in synchronization of assessments, standardization of tests, the initiation of new NAP projects, and the granting of the SIGMA award. JEM partners UvA and TU/e are SIGMA members.

Telmme, (Technology Enhanced Learning for Mathematical Master Education) is a new Dutch funded project in which TU/e will contribute, together with TU Delft and U Twente, to setup an elearning site for students having to overcome mathematical deficiencies upon entering a technical master program. The site will offer elearning material, exercises and tests in the areas of calculus, linear algebra and statistics and stochastics. The project is partially funded by the SURF foundation and will start in September 2009. A first demo version of the portal is already up at (<http://dam02.win.tue.nl/elmi>). TU/e also reports that in the past year over 1000 students have carried out 50000 exercises on their site Wortel TU/e (<http://wortel.tue.nl>).

FETLAR, Finding Electronic Teaching Learning and Assessment Resources, is the UK MSOR community's bid through the Subject Centre strand for the Open Educational Resources (OER) call from HEFCE/JISC (<http://www.fetlar.bham.ac.uk/>). This project takes place in the pilot phase to encourage and enable the open sharing of educational resources. The FETLAR project addresses the challenge associated with students' mathematical skills and competencies on transition into higher education and the need to raise the retention rate of first-year students on science and engineering courses. JEM partner UB is the coordinating manager of FETLAR.

MARCH-et, (Make Relevant Choices in Educational Technology), accepted in the National Action Programme e-Learning of the Dutch SURF Foundation, regarding the use of ICT in university education, and the development of modules that can be used in professional training of university staff.

Mobile phone assisted learning in Nicaragua, UH has also been granted a fund for writing a project proposal within the framework higher education institutions capacity building projects of the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland. The intent is to bring the expertise of UH in online mathematics to improve the use of ICT at the Mathematics department of Universidad Centroamericana in Nicaragua.

8.2 International funding

SCIENCE, [Symbolic Computation Infrastructure for Europe](#), brings together the developers of four powerful symbolic computation software packages and a major symbolic computation research institute supported by research groups expert in essential underpinning technologies, to unite the European community of researchers in, and users of, symbolic computation. The project will promote the development of new software made more efficient by sharing components and expertise, more interoperable in the modern Web services environment and ready for the coming environment of Grid computing. The project is an *Integrated Infrastructure Initiative*, funded by the European Commission under the Research Infrastructures Action of Framework 6. It began on 1 April 2006 and runs for 5 years. JEM partner TU/e is part of the Consortium.

InterGeo, Interoperable Interactive Geometry for Europe is a EU co-funded eContentPlus project aiming at making digital content for mathematics teaching, more specifically dynamic geometric resources, in Europe more accessible, usable and exploitable. The project started in October 2007 and will end in September 2010. JEM partners Maths For More and TU/e are part of the InterGeo consortium.

MOLTO, Multilingual Online Translation is a project proposal to the European Commission coordinated by CTH with the participation of UPC and UH that has reached negotiation stage. MOLTO's goal is to develop a set of tools for translating texts between multiple languages in real time with high quality. Languages are separate modules in the tool and can be varied; prototypes covering a majority of the EU's 23 official languages will be built, in particular one for mathematical exercises.

Establishing Web-Based Mathematical Learning Systems, UH is partner in a Leonardo Da Vinci project coordinated by the Turkish University Selcuk that will start in the Autumn 2009.

8.3 Sustainability

The sustainability of the deliverables of publicly funded projects requires special attention. In the case of the JEM project, the main deliverable is the increased collaboration between various parties in the area of elearning mathematics. This increased collaboration has been instrumental in obtaining funding for several of the new projects listed above. The ideas of the JEM Network will continue in these new projects.

UH will take over the hosting of the JEM website, and the site will remain fully functional. The technologies developed for the JEM website will also be implemented to create a new website for the European Mathematical Society. This marks a significant enhancement of web services of European mathematics educators.

University of Helsinki is investigating possible commercial and community service uses of the open source and other third party web technologies collected to the JEM website. An important outreach is the planned use of moodle in mathematics education in developing countries. This is triggered by JEM experiences, and would mark a new direction in the developmental aid offered by the Finnish government. Such developmental aid projects will, on the other hand, also provide resources that guarantee the sustainability of the work of the JEM network. One such developmental aid project is presently underway.